

The Effect of Service Quality and Customer Value on Customer Satisfaction in Retail Industry

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of service quality and customer value of Indomaret and Alfamart on satisfaction. The research design used in this study is explanatory design. The location of this research is Bekasi with the object of research being two mini markets. The research data uses primary data by distributing questionnaires to respondents, the data were analyzed using SPSS. The results of this study indicate that service quality and customer value have an influence on customer satisfaction. Median calculation results of service quality and customer value indicate that Alfamart is smaller than Indomaret. while the Median customer satisfaction perceived by Alfamart customers is greater than Indomaret.

Keywords: Service Quality, Customer Value, Satisfaction.

1. Introduction

Indonesia with a population of 252 million, 50% of whom are productive age. This makes Indonesia the most potential market in Southeast Asia. Indonesia's GDP per capita of US \$ 3,500 exceeds competitor countries in ASEAN such as the Philippines and Vietnam. The number of households in Indonesia with an annual budget of around the US \$ 5,000-US \$ 15,000 is estimated to expand from 36% at present to 58% in 2020. More than 60 million low-income residents are projected to join the middle class in the coming decade, thus encourage stronger consumer demand. The total market for the consumer goods industry in Indonesia in 2030 is estimated to be the US \$ 810 billion.

Consumer spending in Indonesia grows at an average annual rate of around 11.8% for the 2012-2015 period. In 2015, consumer spending on food was estimated at Rp 1,930 trillion, while non-food products amounted to Rp 4,369 trillion. The modern trade industry for the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) category in Indonesia grew by an average of 10.8% in 2015, with the highest growth occurring in the minimarket segment by 11% and super / hypermarkets at 10.6%. Modern shop sales per capita in Indonesia are estimated at the US \$ 60 with a composition of 56% in minimarkets and 44% in super / hypermarkets. The market size of the minimarket industry in Indonesia is around IDR 73 trillion with an annual average growth of 13.5% for the period 2012-2015. In 2015, the highest sales growth in the modern retail industry was experienced by the personal care segment by 12.7%, while the lowest sales were pharmaceutical products at 1.8%.

Tight competition in the minimarket, convenience, and super / hypermarket segments. Alfamart carried by PT Sumber Alfaria Trijaya Tbk (AMRT) competes with PT Indomart (Indomaret) and 7-Eleven made by PT Modern International Tbk (MDRN). While in the super / hypermarket segment, Hero competes with Hypermart which is carried by PT Matahari Putra Prima Tbk (MPPA).

In addition, the growth of the increase in outlets of each company was shown from Alfamart, Indomart, 7-eleven, Hero (Giant), and Hypermart (MPPA Retail Group). Do not forget to display expansion strategies, trends in income and profits, and financial ratios of each retailer.

The problem of service is actually not a difficult or complicated thing, but if this is not considered, it can cause things that are vulnerable because of its very sensitive nature. The service system needs to be supported by quality services, adequate facilities, and ethics or manners. While the purpose of providing services is to provide satisfaction to consumers / customers so that the resulting added value for the company.

Based on the identification of problems and constraints of the problems that have been determined, the problem of this research can be formulated descriptively as follows: "the influence of service quality and customer value on customer satisfaction in the retail industry. in addition, it also compares service quality, customer value, and customer satisfaction at Alfamart with Indomaret.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Service Quality

Service quality is defined as a comparison of expected service with services perceived by consumers both through information and customer experience received.

2.2 Dimensions of Service Quality

Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1988) state that there are 10 categories of Service Quality. The 10 categories according to them could be overlapping because they build them through exploratory studies which in fact use a qualitative approach. After conducting a series of validity and reliability tests, five determinants were found as dimensions of service quality, namely:

1. Reliability, related to the company's ability to provide accurate services from the first time without any errors and to prepare services in accordance with the agreed time;
2. Responsiveness, with regard to the willingness and ability of employees to help consumers and respond to their requests, and inform when services will be provided and then provide services quickly.
3. Assurance, namely the behavior of employees is able to foster consumer confidence in the company and the company can create a sense of security for its customers. Guarantees also mean that employees are always polite and master the knowledge and skills needed to deal with any consumer questions or problems.
4. Empathy means that the company understands the problems of its customers and acts in the interests of consumers, and gives personal attention to consumers and has comfortable operating hours.
5. Tangibles, with regard to the attractiveness of the physical facilities of the equipment, and the materials used by the company, as well as the appearance of employees.

Other researchers, namely Groonroos (1990) determined 3 dimensions of service quality, namely:

1. Technical or outcome dimension, related to what consumers receive.
2. Functional or process-related dimension, relating to how the service is delivered or presented.
3. Corporate image, that is related to the corporate image of the consumer.

Fitzsimmons and Fitzsimmons (2011) also establish 4 dimensions of service quality, namely:

1. Care and concern, that is the feeling of the consumer for the full attention and concern of the company, employees and the operating system aimed at solving the problem at hand.
2. Spontaneity, that is real action from personnel who show a strong and spontaneous desire to help solve problems or difficulties faced by consumers.
3. Problem solving, namely the expertise of the contact person to carry out the task carefully and follow the standard procedures set.
4. Recovery, that is a special effort taken if something goes wrong or is not expected to occur.

The dimensions used in this study are tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

2.1 Customer Value

Based on several theoretical foundations of customer value, it can be hypothesized that customer value is the overall assessment of the consumer's benefits of a product based on perceptions of what they have received and what they have given. Customer value can be measured by 3 indicators, namely: 1) Benefits comparable to the money spent, 2) The price is reasonable / reasonable, and 3) Purchases that are useful.

3. Research Method

This research is a quantitative study, the study population is consumers of Indomaret and Alfamart minimarkets in Bekasi. The sampling technique in this study used non probability sampling techniques, namely sampling techniques that provide equal opportunities for each element (member) of the population to be selected as sample members.

4. Analysis and Discussion

4.1 Validity Test

4.1.1 Validity Test at Alfa Midi

Validity and reliability test results are based on the calculation results

Table 4.1.1
Validity Test Results

Indicator	r count	r table	Information
Tangible 1	.761	0,2732	Valid
Tangible 2	.668	0,2732	Valid
Tangible 3	.546	0,2732	Valid
Reliability 1	.524	0,2732	Valid
Reliability 2	.604	0,2732	Valid
Responsiveness 1	.459	0,2732	Valid
Responsiveness 2	.682	0,2732	Valid
Responsiveness 3	.518	0,2732	Valid
Assurance 1	.547	0,2732	Valid
Assurance 2	.593	0,2732	Valid
Assurance 3	.593	0,2732	Valid
Empathy 1	.538	0,2732	Valid
Empathy 2	.663	0,2732	Valid
Customer Value 1	.370	0,2732	Valid
Customer Value 2	.510	0,2732	Valid
Customer Value 3	.610	0,2732	Valid
Satisfaction 1	.831	0,2732	Valid
Satisfaction 2	.888	0,2732	Valid
Satisfaction 3	.823	0,2732	Valid
Satisfaction 4	.654	0,2732	Valid

4.1.2 Validity Test at Indomaret

Validity and reliability test results are based on the calculation results

Table 4.1.2
Validity Test Result

Indicator	r count	r table	Information
Tangible 1	.756	0,2732	Valid
Tangible 2	.736	0,2732	Valid
Tangible 3	.802	0,2732	Valid
Reliability 1	.703	0,2732	Valid
Reliability 2	.693	0,2732	Valid
Responsiveness 1	.656	0,2732	Valid
Responsiveness 2	.620	0,2732	Valid
Responsiveness 3	.582	0,2732	Valid
Assurance 1	.707	0,2732	Valid
Assurance 2	.668	0,2732	Valid
Assurance 3	.755	0,2732	Valid
Empathy 1	.765	0,2732	Valid
Empathy 2	.673	0,2732	Valid
Customer Value 1	.611	0,2732	Valid
Customer Value 2	.574	0,2732	Valid
Customer Value 3	.466	0,2732	Valid
Satisfaction 1	.794	0,2732	Valid
Satisfaction 2	.872	0,2732	Valid
Satisfaction 3	.824	0,2732	Valid
Satisfaction 4	.606	0,2732	Valid

4.2. Reliability Test Result

Reliability test carried out in this study the authors sought reliability using the Cronbach Alpha technique. A variable is declared reliable if it produces a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.50 (Suyiono, 2014:87). In this study, we will see the results of Cronbach's Alpha for each variable in the questionnaire data that has been filled by 30 respondents.

Table 4.1.3
Reliability Test Result

No	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Item	Information
1	Service Quality at Alfa	0,894	13	Reliable
2	Service Quality at Indomaret	0,936	13	Reliable
3	Customer Value at Alfa	0,679	3	Reliable
4	Customer Value at Indo Maret	0,730	3	Reliable
5	Satisfaction of Alfa	0,910	4	Reliable
6	Satisfaction of Indomaret	0,894	4	Reliable

Source: Processed Researchers, 2018

based on table 4.1.3 states that each dimension description has Cronbach Alpha > 0.50 . That is, research on the statements of the above variables is stated to be reliable because it has a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.50 .

4.3. Classic assumption test

4.3.1 Normality Test at Alfa

Testing of the classic assumptions of normality aims to find out whether the data residuals from the linear regression model have a normal distribution or not. There are two ways to detect whether the residual data is normally distributed or not by looking at the normal probability plotline and the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test statistical test. If the normal probability line plot shows that the scattered points coincide around the diagonal line and in the direction of the diagonal line, this can be concluded that the residual data has a normal distribution or that the data meets the classical assumption of normality. Further in the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test One-Sample test. If the significance value is more than 0.05, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed (Latan and Temalagi, 2013: 56). Below are the results of the normality test:

The Histogram pattern appears to follow the normal curve, even though there are some data that appear outlier, but in general, the data distribution follows the normal curve, so it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

4.3.2. Normality Test at Indo Maret

The Histogram pattern appears to follow the normal curve, even though there are some data that appear outlier, but in general, the data distribution follows the normal curve, so it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

4.3.3 Heteroscedasticity Test Results at Alfa

Heteroscedasticity Test Results at Alfa

Dari Hasil Gambar 4.3.3. terlihat bahwa Gambar *scatterplot* memiliki pola yang menyebar secara acak dan titik-titik menyebar diatas dan dibawah angka 0 pada sumbu Y, Hal ini Dapat disimpulkan bahwa model regresi linear berganda terbebas dari asumsi klasik heteroskedastisitas.

4.3.4 Heteroscedasticity Test Results at Indo Maret

Heteroscedasticity Test Results at Indomaret

based on figure 4.3.4 it can be seen that the scatterplot image has a pattern that spreads randomly and the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis, it can be concluded that multiple linear regression models are free from the classical assumption of heteroscedasticity.

4.3.5. Multicollinearity Test at Alfa

The second classic assumption test is the multicollinearity test. Testing of the classic assumption of multicollinearity aims to determine whether or not there is a correlation between independent variables in the regression model. The classic multicollinearity assumption test can only be done if there is more than one independent variable in the regression. The general way used by researchers to detect the presence or absence of multicollinearity problems in the regression model is the value of Tolerance and VIP (Valiance Inflation Factor) the recommended value for the absence of multicollinearity problems is the Tolerance value must be > 0.10 and VIP value <10 (Hair et al. quoted by Latan and Temalangi, 2013: 63).

**Table 4.3.5
Multicollinearity Test at Alfa**

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.090	1.259		1.660	.103		
	Service Quality	.099	.306	.047	.324	.747	.952	1.051
	Customer Value	.194	.192	.146	1.009	.318	.952	1.051

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

4.3.6. Multicollinearity Test at Indomaret

Table 4.3.6-Multicollinearity Test at IndoMaret

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-2.129	.685		-3.110	.003		
	Service Quality	1.090	.174	.561	6.280	.000	.886	1.129
	Custoer Value	.673	.142	.422	4.724	.000	.886	1.129

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

The second classic assumption test is the multicollinearity test. Testing of the classic assumption of multicollinearity aims to determine whether or not there is a correlation between independent variables in the regression model. The classic multicollinearity assumption test can only be done if there is more than one independent variable in the regression. The general way used by researchers to detect the presence or absence of multicollinearity problems in the regression model is the value of Tolerance and VIP (Valiance Inflation Factor) the recommended value for the absence of multicollinearity problems is the Tolerance value must be > 0.10 and VIP value <10 (Hair et al. quoted by Latan and Temalangi, 2013: 63).

4.4. T Test

4.4.1.T test at Alfamart

Analysis of the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction at Alfa

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.537	1.179		2.152	.036		
	Service Quality	.167	.298	.079	.559	.579	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

Based on the results of the coefficients or t test results obtained t count of 0.036 with a significance level of 0.000. based on the results of coefficients stated that service quality has t count of 0.559 > 0.05, this means that service quality affects customer satisfaction.

Analysis of the effect of customer value on customer satisfaction at alfamart

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.429	.694		3.501	.001		
	Customer Value	.208	.186	.156	1.118	.269	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

Based on the results of the test coefficients or t test obtained t count of 3.501 with a significance level of 0.000. based on the results of coefficients stated that customer value has t count of 1.118 > 0.05, this means that customer value affects customer satisfaction.

4.4.2 T Test at Indomaret

Analysis of the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction at Indomaret

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.847	.751		-1.129	.264		
	Service Quality	1.367	.195	.704	7.007	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

Based on the results of the test coefficients or t test obtained t count of -1.129 with a significance level of 0.000. based on the results of coefficients states that service quality has a t count of 7, 007 > 0.05 this means that service quality affects customer satisfaction.

Analysis of the effect of customer value on customer satisfaction at Indomaret

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.964	.632		1.524	.134		
	Customer Value	.975	.178	.612	5.469	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

Based on the test results of coefficients or t test obtained t count of 1.524 with a significance level of 0.000. based on the results of coefficients stated that customer value has t count of 5.469 > 0.05 this means that customer value affects customer satisfaction.

4.5. Independent Test

Group Statistics					
	groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Service Quality	alfamart	52	3.9295	.41829	.05801
	indomaret	52	3.7981	.61307	.08502

The mean mean quality value for Alfamart is 3.9 with a standard deviation of 0.41 and the average value of Indomart quality is 3.7 with a standard deviation of 0.61

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Service Quality	Equal variances assumed	4.583	.035	1.277	102	.204	.13146	.10292	-.07268	.33560
	Equal variances not assumed			1.277	90.026	.205	.13146	.10292	-.07301	.33593

F test analysis

Hypothesis H0: Both population variances are homogeneous

Hypothesis H1: Both population variances are not equal (not homogeneous)

Decision-making

If the probability value is > 0.05, then H0 is accepted

If the probability value is <0.05, then H0 is rejected

Decision:

It can be seen that F counts for the quality value of 4,583 with a probability of 0.035. Because the probability value is <0.05, H0 is rejected or the two population variances are not the same.

T Test Analysis

Hypothesis

H0: Average - the quality value between Indomart and Alfamart is the same

H1: The average quality value between Indomart and Alfamart is not the same

Based on the probability value:

If the probability is > 0.05 then H0 is accepted

If the probability is <0.05 then H0 is rejected

T count with a probability value of 1,277. Because probability > 0.05, H0 is accepted, it can be concluded that the average index of quality values between alpha and indomart is the same

Group Statistics					
	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Customer Value	Alfamart	52	3.6731	.66500	.09222
	Indomaret	52	3.4679	.74757	.10367

The mean mean quality value for Alfamart is 3.6 with a standard deviation of 0.66 and the average value of Indomart quality is 3.4 with a standard deviation of 0.74

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Customer Value	Equal variances assumed	.751	.388	1.478	102	.142	.20513	.13875	-.07008	.48034
	Equal variances not assumed			1.478	100.634	.142	.20513	.13875	-.07013	.48038

F test analysis

Hypothesis H0: Both population variances are homogeneous

Hypothesis H1: Both population variances are not equal (not homogeneous)

Decision-making

If the probability value is > 0.05 , then H0 is accepted

If the probability value is < 0.05 , then H0 is rejected

Decision:

It can be seen that the F count for customer value is 0.751 with probability 0.388. Because the probability value is > 0.05 then H0 is accepted or both population variances are the same

T Test Analysis

Hypothesis

H0: The average value of the customer between Indomart and Alfamart is the same

H1: The average customer value between Indomart and Alfamart is not the same

Based on the probability value:

If the probability is > 0.05 then H0 is accepted

If the probability is < 0.05 then H0 is rejected

T count with a probability value of 1.478. Because probability > 0.05 then H0 is accepted, it can be concluded that the average customer value index between alpha and indomart is the same

Group Statistics					
	kelompok	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Satisfaction	alfamart	52	3.1923	.88508	.12274
	indomart	52	4.3462	1.19177	.16527

The mean mean quality value for Alfamart is 3.1 with a standard deviation of 0.88 and the average value of Indomaret quality is 4.3 with a standard deviation of 1.19

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Satisfaction	Equal variances assumed	2.990	.087	-5.605	102	.000	-1.15385	.20586	-1.56217	-.74552
	Equal variances not assumed			-5.605	94.136	.000	-1.15385	.20586	-1.56258	-.74511

F test analysis

Hypothesis H0: Both population variances are homogeneous

Hypothesis H1: Both population variances are not equal (not homogeneous)

Decision-making

If the probability value is > 0.05 , then H0 is accepted

If the probability value is < 0.05 , then H0 is rejected

Decision:

It can be seen that F count for customer satisfaction is 2.990 with probability 0.087. Because the probability value is > 0.05 then H0 is accepted or both population variances are the same

T Test Analysis

Hypothesis

H0: Average - the average customer satisfaction between Indomart and Alfamart is the same

H1: The average customer satisfaction between Indomart and Alfamart is not the same

Based on the probability value:

If the probability is > 0.05 then H0 is accepted

If the probability is < 0.05 then H0 is rejected

T count with a probability value of $-5,605$. Because probability > 0.05 then H0 is accepted, it can be concluded that the average customer value index between alpha and indomart is the same

4.6. Mean

The mean value of Alfamart and Indomaret

No	Information	Alfamart	Indomaret	Conclusion
1	Appearance clerk who was dressed neatly minimarket	3,8	3,6	Alfa>Indo
2	This minimarket neatly	3,7	3,5	Alfa>Indo
3	The equipment used for transactions at the minimarket has met the needs	3,9	3,9	Alfa=Indo
4	Officers in this minimarket have the ability to serve	4,1	4,1	Alfa=Indo
5	Officers at the minimarket are willing to provide answers in accordance with applicable regulations	3,8	3,8	Alfa=Indo
6	This Mini Market provides good service	3,7	3,7	Alfa=Indo
7	This Mini Market opens a shop on time	3,7	3,6	Alfa>Indo
8	The officers in the minimarket are responsive to consumer questions	3,9	3,6	Alfa>Indo
9	Officers in the minimarket are polite in serving consumers	3,7	3,5	Alfa>Indo
10	Officers in the minimarket are friendly in serving consumers	4,0	3,7	Alfa>Indo
11	Officers in the minimarket are able to communicate well	3,9	3,6	Alfa>Indo
12	Officers at the minimarket have a sensitivity to the problems faced by consumers when shopping	3,4	3,5	Alfa<Indo
13	Officers at the minimarket have concerns about the problems faced by consumers	3,5	3,8	Alfa<Indo
14	This mini market sells quality product products in accordance with the value that I spend	3,5	3,3	Alfa>Indo
15	Shopping at this minimarket provides added value compared to other minimarkets	3,6	3,4	Alfa>Indo
16	Shopping at this mini-market is cheaper than other minimarkets	3,4	3,4	Alfa=Indo
17	The price offered with the value issued at this minimarket is as expected	3,1	2,9	Alfa>Indo
18	The services offered at this minimarket are as expected	3,1	3,1	Alfa=Indo
19	Products offered at this minimarket are quality	3,1	3,1	Alfa=Indo
20	This mini market is a quality minimarket	3,2	3,5	Alfa<Indo

4.7. Discussion

1. Based on the average value obtained for the appearance of the minimarket attendant who is well-dressed and this Minimarket is neatly arranged Alfamart is higher meaning neatly both the officer and the arrangement are neater.
2. The equipment used for the minimarket transaction has met the needs, the existing minimarket officer has the ability to serve, the minimarket existing officer is willing to provide answers in accordance with the applicable provisions, this mini Market provides good service, between Indomaret and alfamart has a service the same one.
3. This Mini Market opens the shop on time. The officer who is minimized is responsive to consumer questions. The officer who is minimized is friendly in serving consumers. The official who is in the market is able to communicate well, the service at Alfamart has a higher average value.
4. This minimized market officer has a sensitivity to the problems faced by consumers when shopping, the officers in this minimarket have concerns about the problems faced by consumers, this mini market is a quality minimarket at Alfamart which has a lower value than at Indomaret.

The researcher observed several things about Alfamart and Indomaret including:

1. The price of goods in Alfamart tends to be expensive because the items are purchased from the distributor. While the prices offered in Indomaret tend to be cheaper because the goods sold in Indomaret are obtained directly from the manufacturer.
2. The buyers are more likely to shop at Indomaret, because the services provided tend to be better. Whereas if we shop at Alfamart, the service provided is not good.
3. Promotion carried out by Alfamart to the community is more effective and fast, while promotions carried out in Indomaret tend to be slow.
4. Indomaret have an ATM machine so that many people and students who want to make money will go to Indomaret and sometimes shop there so that they can more efficiently time and energy. Whereas in Alfamart there is no ATM machine.
5. Alfamart has CCTV, while Indomaret does not have CCTV, so the level of supervision in Indomaret is lacking.
6. Indomaret is wider than Alfamart.
7. Availability of products between the two minimarkets is quite balanced. Many and varied. In Indonesia, there are fewer brands of ice cream that are sold while if we shop at Alfamart sell various brands of ice cream.
8. Alfamart is equipped with facilities in the form of mirrors, so customers can reflect as they please. While Indomaret does not have a mirror.
9. Indomaret has facilities such as television and music, so we can watch how Indomaret services while in Alfamart only in the form of music.
10. Arranging shelves in Indomaret shorter than Alfamart Alfamart comes with a convenience store but in small amounts
11. Indomaret also won because it has been innovating with Indomaret plus and points with many locations accompanied by a wider, medium location seat, from its own layout sector I am somewhat less interested in alpha ex: for the arrangement of gallon water in alpha not provided where the gallon is stacked, indomaret is more organized

5. Conclusion

1. Based on the test results of the coefficients or t test obtained t count equal to 0.036 with a significance level of 0.000. based on the results of coefficients stated that service quality has t count of $0.559 > 0.05$, this means that service quality affects customer satisfaction.
2. Based on the test results of the coefficients or t test obtained t count of 3.501 with a significance level of 0.000. based on the results of coefficients stated that customer value has t count of $1.118 > 0.05$, this means that customer value affects customer satisfaction
3. Based on the test results of the coefficients or t test obtained t count of -1.129 with a significance level of 0.000. based on the results of coefficients states that service quality has at the count of $7,007 > 0.05$ this means that service quality affects customer satisfaction.
4. Based on the test results of the coefficients or t test obtained t count of 1.524 with a significance level of 0.000. based on the results of coefficients stated that customer value has t count of $5.469 > 0.05$ this means that customer value affects customer satisfaction.
5. The median quality of services provided by Alfamart is slower than the median quality of services provided by Indomaret
6. The median customer value given Alfamart is smaller than the median value of the customer given by Indomaret
7. Median customer satisfaction perceived by Alfamart customers is greater than the median customer satisfaction given by Indomaret

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